

Yashil IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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IMPLEMENTATION AND USE OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN LOGISTICS ABSTRACT

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Abstract: The article examines issues of improving efficiency in logistics through the use of digital technologies. Digital technologies have become so embedded in our lives that today not only our daily activities, but also the development of socio-economic spheres cannot be imagined without them. Naturally, as in other fields, the introduction of digital technologies in the field of logistics is also fundamentally changing its activities. It is not only about the relationship between logistics companies, drivers and shippers.

Key words: digital transformation, digital technologies, innovative approach.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada raqamli texnologiyalardan foydalanish orqali logistika samaradorligini oshirish masalalari ko'rib chiqiladi. Raqamli texnologiyalar hayotimizga shu qadar singib ketganki, bugungi kunda nafaqat kundalik faoliyatimiz, balki ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy sohalar rivojini ham ularsiz tasavvur etib bo'lmaydi. Tabiiyki, boshqa sohalarda bo'lgani kabi logistika sohasida ham raqamli texnologiyalarning joriy etilishi uning faoliyatini tubdan o'zgartirmoqda. Bu nafaqat logistika kompaniyalari, haydovchilar va jo'natuvchilar o'rtasidagi munosabatlar haqida.

Kalit so'zlar: raqamli transformatsiya, raqamli texnologiyalar, innovatsion yondashuv.

Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются вопросы повышения эффективности логистики за счет использования цифровых технологий. Цифровые технологии настолько прочно вошли в нашу жизнь, что сегодня без них невозможно представить не только нашу повседневную деятельность, но и развитие социально-экономических сфер. Естественно, как и в других сферах, внедрение цифровых технологий в сфере логистики также кардинально меняет ее деятельность. Речь идет не только об отношениях между логистическими компаниями, водителями и грузоотправителями.

Ключевые слова: цифровая трансформация, цифровые технологии, инновационный подход.

INTRODUCTION

Uzbekistan is at the stage of transition to digital economy. According to him, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 5, 2020 No. President's decision-6079 "On approval of the strategy of DIGITAL UZBEKISTAN – 2030 and measures for its effective implementation" opened a new page in the policy of transition to digital economy in our country ^[1].

The strategy defines the strategic goals, priorities and medium- and long-term prospective tasks of the development of the digital economy and electronic government of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as serves as a basis for the wider introduction of digital technologies based on the priorities set in the UN Sustainable Development Goals and the rating of the development of electronic government. does.

In particular, the implementation of more than 220 priority projects aimed at improving the electronic government system, further developing the local market of software products and information technologies, establishing IT parks in all regions of the republic, as well as providing the sector with qualified personnel has begun.

In addition, the complex program “Digital Tashkent” is being implemented, which envisages the launch of a geoportal integrated with more than 40 information systems, the creation of an information system for the management of public transport and communal infrastructure, digitization of the social sphere, and the subsequent implementation of this experience in other regions.

To the topic about of literature analysis.

Under digital technologies is understood a system that uses special methods of encoding and distributing information, which allows solving various problems in a short time.

As the transition to the digital economy transforms all industries, so will logistics. All participants of the logistics process: trade partners, transport participants, insurance and achieved through information integration of customs authorities and logistics companies. To ensure this integration, companies introduce digital technologies into their operations. All this contributes to the emergence of the new term “digital logistics”. In the article “The main directions of digital logistics”, the authors VL Vasilenok, VV Negreeva, EI Aleksashkina, AI Kruglov and SA Plastunova define digital logistics as a method of information search, storage and transmission, as well as digital technologies that allow to optimize the process of cargo delivery [2]. Thus, the authors studying this topic emphasized the importance of introducing digital technologies to increase the efficiency of logistics organizations.

RESEARCH METHODOLOG

The following methods and methods were used in writing the article: system analysis, details, factor analysis on increasing efficiency in logistics through the use of digital technologies, and the opinions of leading scientists were studied.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

One of the technologies used in logistics is blockchain technology (English. Blockchain). Blockchain is a permanent block chain method of storing information. It is recorded in the form of blocks in the method under investigation a shared account shared by network servers that records transaction reports. This technology is a type of “Distributed Ledger Technology” technology.

According to a study conducted by Deloitte (an international network of consulting and audit services companies), 74% of all respondents said that their company's use of blockchain is “economically reliable”, and the majority of them indicated that they already use this technology. In addition, almost 40% of respondents reported that their companies will invest at least 5 million dollars in the next year [3]. In turn, Gartner (research and consulting company specializing in information technology markets) analysts in September 2019, which industries need recommended that this blockchain consists of others [1-15]. By using the continuity of supply chains, tracking the movement of goods, the government improves customs operations and increases the level of transparency arising from the composition of products.

Blockchains make it possible to create, store and record a digital ledger of transactions in several places at the same time. It is believed that blockchain technology only works with money transactions, but now this technology can be used in any field that has blocks related to information. Recently, blockchain has increasingly started to be used in logistics as a means of ensuring the transparency of transactions with goods throughout the supply chain, reducing the risk of using electronic document circulation and other digital technologies. At the same time, a high level of information security and protection of personal and commercial data is ensured [4].

The main principle of blockchain technology is the use of blocks of information stored in a distributed network. The data in the blocks is processed, verified, which ensures the continuity of data and transactions and remains unchanged. Thus, the data can be changed only with the consent of all participants involved. Transparency is achieved by hiding information from all parties not involved in the process.

Blockchain technology, also “smart contracts” make up enable will give

fulfillment of obligations of contracts, monitoring and computer program checks. When these two technologies are used, contracts are transparent to all parties involved by managed and in them data will remain unchanged. Smart contracts allow the use of automatic dispute resolution [5]. A comparison of ordinary contracts with smart ones is presented in the table. (Table 1)

Table 1: Traditional and smart contracts comparison

COMPARISON AREA	TRADITIONAL CONTRACT	SMART CONTRACT
The operation execution time	1-3 day	A minute
Money funds transfer	Manually	Automatic
Value	Expensive	Very cheap
Availability	Physical	Virtual
Signature	Hand with	Virtual (numerical)
A lawyer participation	Necessary	perhaps no need
Errors probability	There is (Human factor)	Minimum

Thus, in many features, a smart contract is superior to a traditional contract: a smart contract is faster, cheaper, more accurate and more convenient, because its conclusion and execution are performed virtually.

The most important feature of the blockchain is the absence of real intermediaries in the transaction system, as well as the verification of transactions and lack of need for an approving regulatory body. This mediation role is performed by a system, a mathematical algorithm, due to which it does not make mistakes. This technology can provide the following advantages for logistics companies:

- the ability to track the product along the supply chain: from the place of production to the final consumer; ^[15]
- it is impossible to make changes in the delivery process without the consent of all participants, and the use of cryptography provides additional security;
- the process by automatically replacing manual processing;
- the ability to track data on the movement of cargo and passengers by regulatory authorities;
- buyers fake didn't happen goods and from scams protection to do; ^[8]
- timely information on the origin of cargo, their characteristics and features, as well as timely payment of customs duties, to obtain information on the status of insurable and payable shipments.

Thus, in the implementation of this technology, the organization not only depends on reliability increase, loads delivery to give in the process mistakes minimize,

rather, it expects to improve the efficiency of the processes supported by the lock.

Blockchain technology can be used for various purposes. Most important is the maintenance of static and dynamic registers used to store data. An example of a static registration can be the registration of the company's assets (vehicles), such registration does not require complex calculations and changes are rarely made to it. ^[18] Dynamic registers differ from static registers in that the information is constantly updated. In logistics, dynamic registers are often used, because carrying out operations with goods and passing through the supply chain of goods receives new information entered into the register. Another important goal is the creation of "smart contracts", which are widely used in the field of logistics. Such contracts are convenient for both parties because they contain algorithmic conditions that work on a predetermined action. For example, after the delivery of the goods to the consumer and about it in the block (in the register), payment for the services performed is made automatically. Another goal is to use blockchain as a payment system. In this case, the clear advantage of this technology is the ability to use crypto-currency (crypto-money) as payment ^[6, 13].

Other digital technologies used in logistics are the Internet of Things (Internet of Things, IoT). This technology is a network that connects different devices and objects over the Internet to transfer data. ^[12]

Many companies in various industries around the world have already implemented this technology. ^[11] On the side of Cisco, an American company that develops and sells more than 50 billion devices in telecommunications network equipment in 2020. Only 17% of these devices were PCs and smartphones. The remaining 83% are smart home systems, gadgets and internet-connected devices. At the same time, PRNewswire estimates the size of the global Internet market as follows: 171 billion dollars. 2017 and 561 billion dollars. 2022 year. In this case, the growth rate will be approximately 27% per year ^[10].

Logistics in the field things Internet technology current of reaching advantages:

- all Real at the time processes ability to observe;
- determine the efficiency of people and vehicles with additional changes to improve efficiency;
- processes automation; ^[14]
- to consumers service display quality increase, satisfaction increase

For consumers, the Internet of Things is also very important. Thus, relevant and accurate information in tracking shipments gives customers confidence in the service and increases their satisfaction.

One of the successful examples of using the Internet is the American company RogueAle's implementation of tools for tracking the supply chain, which allows tracking the transportation of perishable products.

Special sensors that collect data on temperature and humidity and transmit it to the staff keep raw materials fresh and suitable for use.

Another example is aimed at increasing traffic safety. Railroad company Union Pacific uses Internet of Things technology to prevent equipment failure and reduce the risk of derailment. It was possible to avoid incidents by placing sensors that monitor the position of the wheels. In this case, the implementation of the technology prevented the company from losing approximately \$40 million per incident ^[16-36].

At the moment, a favorable environment is being created for the transformation of the logistics sector through Internet of Things technology. This is the development of the mobile application market, the use of user devices in the corporate IT system, and the emergence of 5G networks having and using them, working with big data. Also, consumers innovative technologies and approaches current to reach more and more are demanding more, which will help the spread and more active implementation of the Internet for logistics companies.

Artificial intelligence refers to the ability of a computer to perform tasks normally associated with intelligent beings. Along with other digital technologies, the introduction of artificial intelligence will help improve the logistics industry and its development.

Logistics company DHL and IBM released a May 2018 "Artificial Intelligence in Logistics" report that reveals some ideas for transforming the industry and developing operating systems with intelligent support. Companies have concluded that artificial intelligence, like technology, has a number of advantages for the logistics industry:

- interactive communication through customer with cooperation improvement; ^[7]
- logistics operational model change possibility;
- loads observation for from the system use; ^[9]
- processes automation ability;
- orders of size change guess to do opportunity ^[16].

In real logistics companies, artificial intelligence can be used for alerts based on future-oriented analytics. In this case, technology is used to identify important events from large amounts of data and make decisions allows to increase the efficiency of logistics business by independently formulating proposals for acceptance and simplifies this process ^[17].

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Thus, considering three digital technologies: blockchain, Internet of Things and artificial intelligence, it is possible to draw conclusions about the advantages of their implementation, as well as possible obstacles.

Blockchain is a relatively new technology for Uzbek business. Practice the main obstacles to increase is the lack of a legal framework regulating the management of this technology. But despite this, many Uzbek companies are already using blockchain to get advantages such as transparency of transactions with goods, conclusion of smart contracts and timely and complete information about cargo. These benefits can improve shipping quality and customer satisfaction.

The Internet of Things is another digital technology introduced to logistics companies. It gives you real-time monitoring of all processes, automation of processes that do not require human intervention, possible subsequent correction with information collect enable will give. in Uzbekistan things Internet The conditions are very favorable for the development of digital technologies, the emergence of 5G networks, as well as the high demands of consumers on logistics companies for the introduction of the Internet of Things. The market for this technology is small and growing pace despite being low 2022 year every resident until the end point

The ability to connect to the Internet with a data transfer speed of no less than 10 Mbit/s defines the perspective of this market.

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